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ABSTRACT

Narcissistic personality is theoretically well defined, it is an inherent characteristic of its owners. One of dominant characteristic of this personality is a self-centered attribute, expressed through arrogance, manipulation, demand, and love of self, greatness feelings, admiration emotions and non-sympathetic approach to others. Such personality is hard to be managed due to their sense of supremacy and are mostly intolerant to criticism or defeat. These characteristic owners also tend to refuse association with employees or people whom they believe to be less than them in excellence. The presence of narcissism as a potential threat in organizations, justifies the need to strategically administer solutions to avoid or mitigate its negative impact on organizational performance. The purpose of this research is to identify the factors which constitute a new measurable concept of narcissistic employee. The findings of this research expected to provide significant insight on how narcissist behavior could be detrimental to organization's sustainable management. In addition, the expected statistical results will contribute in generating check points concerning the identified symptoms of such phenomena.

Keywords: Narcissistic personality, Self-Centric, Stubborn Hope, Fickle-Mindedness, Over- Estimation, Egotism.

1. INTRODUCTION

Narcissism at workplace is quite unpredictable. The presence of a narcissist employee in an organization is a serious issue in human resource management in general which affects the organizational behavior in specific. A crucial indicator of a narcissistic member is the organization is his/her ability to take undue credit and advantage of someone else's effort and contribution. A narcissistic presence in any organization can disrupt the alignment of employees' effort to the organizational goals as it is quite common for the narcissistic employees to take on unproductive or ineffectual behavior at work, especially when they feel their self-esteem is at threat. Narcissism in organizational psychology is a personality feature in comparison to an affected mind. It is seen to exist in all individuals, although in varying intensities. The significance of this research is to identify the roles of personality and values in determining work behaviors and how it affects the management of daily practices. In addition, the research clarifies key set of behaviors which have indirect influences on management performance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to recent research, the personality profile of narcissist suggests perceptions of exceptionally low modesty and amicability along with low empathy and low meticulousness (Visser et al., 2017).

Narcissism apart from being one of the darkest traits is also a personality mannerism as well as an ailment. Due to this reason, it is more usual that this characteristic is to be treated normal as a narcissistic person, in adverse to Machiavellianism and Psychopathy, are extroverts in nature and maintain positive correlation with openness. Other characteristics of this trait include pride, egotism and short of empathy.

Paunonen et al. (2006) symbolizes narcissism with features of self-centered, self-worth and the negative traits of sides of manipulative and personality grandeur.

In contrast, Galvin et al., in the year 2010 assessed narcissistic behavior as a more complete concept than contrasting the negative and positive sides of the same personality. His study established that the charismatic and passionate quality of narcissistic employee who is also risk taker at work would bring glory to them by leaving behind the organization. Ryan et al. (2019) attached in part the narcissistic to self-determination theory, which find an avenue for those who are looking to improve their traits and behavior.

Popper (2002) in their research state that narcissistic leaders likely represent weak attachment traits than their minimalist narcissistic counterparts. These findings affirm that narcissistic leaders are great at communicating and challenging visions, yet, fail mostly to connect with their followers, who are to implement these visions in the long run.

A serious consequence of narcissism at work is that it weakens the bonding between humans instead of nurturing it. Narcissists are usually detrimental in team environment requiring cooperation and acknowledgement as they are interpersonal uncompromising and indifferent while in teams.

Absence of team spirit at work place hinders the growth of the entire organization and affects the team efforts. Khatak et al., (2018) was tested manager-employee narcissism congruence elicit which has indirect effects on overall performance.

Due to the narcissistic person's urge for power and privilege, they seek special treatments and if it is not received, they turn to rage and fury. In their psychological state of mind, narcissists are susceptible to criticism. Hence, they quickly feel hurt; tend to overreact and get self-protective.

The narcissist expects relentless praise and acknowledgement at work and at the same time underestimate the attributes of peers (Horowitz, 2009). They ensure they claim for the accomplishments if success is the result and if negative, they tend to quickly blame others for the mishap (Miller & Campbell, 2010).

Stress is high at the workplace due to extreme depression, which raises the stress levels at work leading to the increased trend of absenteeism and staff falls out as well (Colligan, T. W., & Higgins, E. M. 2006).

In long-term when the highly efficient employees under a narcissistic supervisor/team leader tend to realize their accomplishments have been sabotaged, they tend to leave the organization thus creating a performance void.

However, to conclude the characteristic of a narcissist, there is just a very thin line of difference between narcissists who are over controlled by their negative traits, making the life of all others difficult and thus hinder organizational progress. In the other aspect if the management is able to identify the symptoms of the narcissistic employee in the early employment stage, the solutions could be developed and treat the narcissistic sources at the right time and place of work. The literature review theoretically has shown there is an impact among research variables, this research will identify the main factors which constitute the frame of reference for identifying narcissist's employee in any organization.

3. METHODS AND STUDY DESIGN

This research adopted an exploratory, descriptive and quantitative methods to identify the presence of narcissistic personality and the significance level of narcissistic behavior in the research field of work.

The researchers were compelled to adopt convenient sampling for data collection using a questionnaire, which required participants with adequate knowledge to understand the research objective and rationale. The research sample comprised of 61 employees from diverse organizations, different positions, different levels and working in different countries.

3.1 Research Model

Based on a summary of theoretical concepts that reflects the agreement of researchers on the factors that stand behind the symptoms of narcissist employee; the research has selected an exploratory approach to fit with the research model. The model is expected to fill the knowledge gap in the field of administrative behavior and management practices with specific focus on the narcissistic moods which are emerging in the daily work at different levels and among various administrative functions.

The worker often behaves without realizing that he is of the narcissistic character or that he carries the symptoms of narcissistic behavior which is reflected negatively on his performance and the performance of the organization as a whole. Based on this theme, the main research questions are formulated as follows:

Q1. Is there a narcissistic personality within the human resources working in the current research community?

Q2. What variables does the factor exploratory analysis reveal within the current research sample?

The researchers assume that many factors stand behind narcissistic phenomena as mentioned in the following hypothesis:

H1: The narcissistic personality is expected to be present in the field of work.

H2: The research variables are expected to be clustered within independent factors reflecting the difference of a narcissistic nature in the present research field.

3.2 Measurement

Factor analysis is used to reduce an attributes related to measure the narcissistic phenomena; content analysis has been followed to construct the general indications which have been observed by scholars as

many details have addressed in the above literature review. The study identified a large number of indicators in the first phase of the content analysis of the concepts related to this phenomenon, with 51 indicators identified.

The indicators were presented to specialists in the subject of narcissism and its various manifestations, where the theoretical validity, face validity and content validity were done on the first scale. A number of indicators were excluded according to expert observations.

After the research team discussed the nature of the changes made to the initial indicators of the research, 20 indicators were drawn which represents the final measure of the current research.

The convenience sampling method has been selected to ensure right to the point answers from 51 respondents.

In order to ensure the achievement of high accuracy results and credibility, the scale was also subjected to the reliability statistics test which is available in the SPSS software, where the scale obtained a high Cronbach's Alpha coefficient (81.5%).

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Management and administrative leadership in particular face a number of problems related to human resources management, including individual moods that are not subject to human profiling or simulation.

It is worth mentioning that the research sample table (1) contributed significantly to the submission of data according to the questionnaire, which included respondents from various managerial and non-managerial levels as well as their place of work in different countries. This contribution is one of the most important factors that led the research team to analyze the results and interpret them in line with the available data.

4.1 Initial Descriptive Results

The results of the analysis of respondents' opinions in itself is one of the research methods which describes what are the characteristics of the population and the phenomenon that is being studied. Both research sample characteristics and descriptive outcomes based on respondents' opinions will be provided as follows:

4.2 Nature of Respondents' Opinions

The observational aspect of this research provided what are the respondent's practices in daily duties and how those practices reflected in actual behavior? (www.questionpro.com).

The quantifiable variables were collected from a purposeful research sample which is expected to be reliable for further statistical analysis. The characteristics of the research sample are presented in table (1) below:

Table (1) Sample Demographic Data

Personal Profile	Status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age	18-29	9	14.8	14.8	14.8
	30-39	13	21.3	21.3	36.1
	40-49	17	27.9	27.9	63.9
	50 and Above	22	36.1	36.1	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	
Gender	Male	43	70.5	70.5	70.5
	Female	18	29.5	29.5	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	
Marital Status	Single	48	78.7	78.7	78.7
	Married	13	21.3	21.3	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	
Experience	Up to 1 year	18	29.5	29.5	29.5
	1-10 years	43	70.5	70.5	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	
Daily office hours	Up to 8 hours	42	68.9	68.9	68.9
	8-10 hours	15	24.6	24.6	93.4
	More than 10 hours	4	6.6	6.6	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	
Job Role at present	Leader & CEO	4	6.6	6.6	6.6
	Manager and section Director	10	16.4	16.4	23.0
	Executive Position	3	4.9	4.9	27.9
	Technical Position	2	3.3	3.3	31.1
	Service Work	7	11.5	11.5	42.6
	College Dean	3	4.9	4.9	47.5
	Program Director	1	1.6	1.6	49.2
	Faculty Lecturer and Teacher	31	50.8	50.8	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	
Qualifications	High School or Professional Certificate	1	1.6	1.6	1.6
	Diploma	1	1.6	1.6	3.3

	Bachelor Degree	12	19.7	19.7	23.0
	Master Degree	17	27.9	27.9	30.8
	PhD	30	49.2	49.2	100.0
	Total	61	100.0	100.0	

The above table presented a segment of the research society which is bearing the characteristics of the purposeful community and represent it with regard to the phenomenon under discussion. The intended features such as (age, gender, marital status, experience, daily work load (DOH), job role and qualifications) have provided a comprehensive contribution from diverse respondent segments. No extreme results observed. The level of qualifications and work experiences have shown high percentages. This will enhance the reliability of opinions as mature contributions are required in such kind of research.

4.3 Nature of Respondents' Opinions

Research respondents' opinion in an actual manner where employee's judgment seems clear in their behavior, actions, comments and attitudes. The data were organized and analyzed through descriptive statistics (table 2). This section identifies the general outcomes to the research question; is there a narcissistic personality within the human resources working in the current research community?

The mean and standard deviation are helpful to identify the emergence of the research phenomena. In addition, research sample opinions as an important observable expression of the group's views, feelings, ideas, beliefs, and attitudes towards the emergence of narcissistic subject at a particular time.

Table (2) Descriptive Statistics

No.	Initial Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Better be alone	3.278	.950
2	Leaking out of secrecy	3.032	1.032
3	I want to prove myself	3.737	0.929
4	Recognition of presence	3.557	1.008
5	Ignorance hurts	3.180	0.991
6	Self-dependency	3.459	1.205
7	Hiding the truths	3.327	1.075
8	Exaggerated feelings of achievement	3.344	1.078
9	Acting like a Hero	2.836	1.051
10	To be a source of reliance	3.049	1.244
11	Pushing to be convinced	2.754	1.135
12	Unstable state of mind	3.016	0.939
13	I am Always right	3.000	0.98
14	Fantasizing attitude for self-recognition	2.852	1.030
15	Not believing in sharing	3.459	0.992
16	Hate to seek advice and support helps	3.508	0.924
17	Dictatorial attitude	3.131	1.024
	Average	3.207	1.035

The results in table (2) provide that there is a narcissistic personality among the research sample employees based on their opinions. The average has shown (3.207) which exceeded the threshold score in such five scales which is equal to (3.00). This result come with clear answer to the first research question and its attached hypothesis.

4.4 Factor Analysis

The research has applied factor analysis- a principal component method. This method is an exploratory approach to identify the most important factors behind the possibility of determining the moods and narcissistic patterns that appear in the field of work. Younus & Al- Dabagh (2011) emphasized that the target for such method does not stand on the exploratory factors, but to consider the consequences of narcissistic behavior which affect the overall daily administrative performance (Younus & Al-Dabagh, 2011).

4.5 Data Reduction And Factors Determination

In order to be able to interpret the factors, it is necessary to observe which set of variables has a greater saturation than a specific factor. Correlation matrix analyzed to find the primary relationship among the variables which should be

excluded if exceeded significant levels of coefficient (0.80) and above.

The correlation matrix as shown in (Appendix 1), does not provide any high correlation coefficient exceeding the specified threshold.

However, the correlation matrix determinant is (0.002), which has exceeded the value of (0.0001). This proves that the variables do not have autocorrelation.

Other measures have used KMO and Bartlett's Test which provide the adequacy of the research sample. The value should exceed the 0.50 to prove the availability of sample adequacy for the purpose of such study table (3). The value of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy is (0.685), this value approves the fulfilment of other significant condition. In addition, the Barlett test also provided the value (333.502), which represents the correlation among the research model variables at statistical significant level ($\alpha=0.000$) which is less than ($\alpha=0.05$). Fulfilment of this condition qualifies the research to use the factor analysis as a relevant tool to answer the research questions and testing its hypothesis.

Table (3)
KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.685
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	333.502
	df	136
	Sig.	.000

4.6 Factors Extraction

However, to use the exploratory analysis method, the correlation matrix was analyzed between the standard variables and then the initial communalities were obtained. The factors were derived depending on the extent of their contribution to the interpretation of the variance. Specifically, those factors with the eigenvalues which should exceed the value (1). The Varimax orthogonal rotation was also used for the research sample.

To proceed further in the process of factor analysis, the principle component analysis- extraction method is performed to find the communalities table (4), which lead to identify the total variance explained in table (5). Consequently, through initial eigenvalues, extraction sums of squared loading and rotation sums of squared loadings, the research come up with the final factors which identifying the main factors that constitute the new research model table (6).

Table (4) Extraction Method Findings (PCA)

No.	Variables	Initial	Extraction
1	Better be alone	1.000	.409
2	Leaking out of secrecy	1.000	.642
3	I want to prove myself	1.000	.690
4	Recognition of presence	1.000	.507
5	Ignorance hurts	1.000	.509
6	Self-dependency	1.000	.650
7	Hiding the truths	1.000	.672
8	Exaggerated feelings of achievement	1.000	.586
9	Acting like a Hero	1.000	.744
10	To be a source of reliance	1.000	.561
11	Pushing to be convinced	1.000	.728
12	Unstable state of mind	1.000	.755
13	I am Always right	1.000	.433
14	Fantasizing attitude for self-recognition	1.000	.600
15	Not believing in sharing	1.000	.772
16	Hate to seek advice and support helps	1.000	.731
17	Dictatorial attitude	1.000	.787

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

It is worth mentioning that any factor with an eigenvalue ≥ 1 explains more variance than a single observed variable (www.theanalysisfactor.com).

As shown in table (5) the first five variables were extracted which captured a certain amount of the overall variance in the observed variables, and five factors are always listed in order of how much variation they explain. The first component factor provides the highest eigenvalue equal to (3.159) from the total variance which explains (63.39).

Table (5) Extracted Factors

Component	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.597	27.042	27.042	4.597	27.042	27.042	3.159	18.582	18.582
2	1.860	10.943	37.985	1.860	10.943	37.985	2.187	12.864	31.446
3	1.616	9.504	47.490	1.616	9.504	47.490	1.834	10.786	42.232
4	1.477	8.688	56.178	1.477	8.688	56.178	1.821	10.711	52.943
5	1.227	7.216	63.394	1.227	7.216	63.394	1.777	10.451	63.394
6	.952	5.601	68.994						
7	.897	5.279	74.274						
8	.806	4.739	79.013						
9	.690	4.059	83.072						
10	.550	3.237	86.309						
11	.501	2.948	89.257						
12	.433	2.549	91.807						
13	.393	2.313	94.120						
14	.314	1.850	95.970						
15	.296	1.744	97.714						
16	.205	1.209	98.922						
17	.183	1.078	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

On the other hand, the following scree plot figure (1) is used to present the number of factors with an eigenvalue

(≥ 1). The point where the slope of the curve is clearly leveling off (the elbow) indicates the number of factors that should be generated by the analysis.

Figure (1) Scree Plot

The extracted factors have listed in the table (6) with the associated correlated components.

Table (6) Rotated Component Matrix

No.	Variables	Component				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Better be alone	.197	.181	.089	.355	.451
2	Leaking out of secrecy	.617	-.162	.255	.255	.324
3	I want to prove myself	.343	.753	.055	-.040	-.034
4	Recognition of presence	.530	.361	.305	-.042	.038
5	Ignorance hurts	.566	.249	.286	.208	-.047
6	Self-dependency	.660	.310	-.221	-.231	.124
7	Hiding the truths	.788	.223	-.040	-.026	-.006
8	Exaggerated feelings of achievement	.328	.401	.165	.522	-.134
9	Acting like a Hero	.066	.387	-.140	.713	.249
10	To be a source of reliance	.024	-.095	.186	.712	-.099
11	Pushing to be convinced	.156	.255	.790	.117	.025
12	Unstable state of mind	.145	-.022	.845	.076	.120
13	I am Always right	.590	-.009	.222	.139	.127
14	Fantazizing attitude for self-recognition	.638	-.180	.136	.374	.030
15	Not believing in sharing	-.043	.828	.150	.235	.090
16	Hate to seek advice and support helps	-.074	.204	.142	-.066	.812
17	Dictatorial attitude	.213	-.280	-.050	-.051	.812

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 18 iterations.

Through a systematic reading of the results displayed in the above table, the research has identified five main factors, as well as the variables that were underlined in

the column of each factor. The correlation coefficients indicated in the correlation matrix indicate which variable is more correlated with the main factor.

The new main factors have been named in terms of compatibility between the logical parameters of the variables and the relevant vocabulary which meet the context of the variables set table (7).

It is worth mentioning that the named factors in our current research are general indicators which indicate the symptoms behind the narcissistic employee in the community of the workplace.

Table (7) Component Factors & Correlated Variables

Factor One (Self-Centric)	Factor Two (Stubborn Hope)	Factor Three (Fickle-Mindfulness)	Factor Four (Over Estimation)	Factor Five (Egotistic)
Leaking out of secrecy	I want to prove myself	Pushing to be convinced	Exaggerated feelings of achievement	Better be alone
Recognition of presence	Not believing in sharing	Unstable state of mind	Acting like a Hero	Hate to seek advice and support helps
Ignorance hurts Self-dependency Hiding the truths I am Always right Fantazizing attitude for self-recognition			To be a source of reliance	Dictatorial attitude

However, the five factors contributed to the interpretation of (63%), data related to the research phenomenon, and these factors may contribute to change if they are adopted as indicators for the primitive planned diagnosis of narcissistic behavior in the organization. This result has come with clear answer to the second research question and its attached hypothesis.

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Narcissism at workplace is quite unpredictable, in this context the current research is exploratory in nature. It has explored new factors to measure the narcissistic personality traits.

Although there are many studies in this area, most of them focused on the descriptive approach on the psychology and psychological aspects, and including the pathological personality associated with personality disorder and mental illness.

Our research approaching the management perspective toward a proactive action for pre-emptive treatment to the expected behavior if emerged in the organization.

It is worth mentioning that the research provided all the necessary conditions associated with the factor

analysis method. The analysis revealed specific logical relationships related to the phenomenon of narcissistic personality in the research community.

The factors derived are calculated according to their contribution to the interpretation of the phenomenon, as follows:

Self-Centric, where this factor is the behavioral symptoms in the form of general traits such as: leaking out of secrecy, recognition of presence, ignorance hurts, self-dependency, hiding the truths, I am always right and fantasizing attitude for self-recognition. All those variables are highly correlated with what we named the self-centric factor personality. This kind of employee putting himself first and only caring about his needs.

I want to prove myself (stubborn hope), where this factor is the behavioral symptoms in the form of employee's traits reflect the concern of proving himself in the work community and he does not believe in sharing good things. This factor also is independent of: other factors and the variables are highly correlated to this factor.

Fickle-Mindedness-where this factor is the behavioral symptoms in the form of: the employee is pushing to be convinced due to unstable state of mind; in short the person is not able to concentrate on one thing and he always jumps from one issue to another without deciding, completing, mastering. This factor with its set of variables is also independent of the other factors in this research.

Over Estimation, where this factor is the behavioral symptoms in the form of: Exaggerated feelings of achievement, acting like a Hero and to be a source of reliance. This type of employee is thinking more extreme than the reality or his abilities to do valued things.

Egoistic as a final factor extracted from this research entails more variables to be addressed such as: The employee prefers to be alone, hate to seek advice or any support from others and acquire a dictatorial attitude. This personality is an overinflated sense of self-worth. Based on the above research conclusion, we suggest that this model may open new avenue for other research area in the behavioral phenomena in the field of human resources management.

The current research findings and associated interpretation have argued, rational aspect of such phenomena.

The extracted variables should be considered as evaluation criteria which assist the leaders in any organization for identifying their employee's general attitudes and behavior in daily work.

The attitude factor is mostly ignored from the points which have been considered in the employee evaluation system, this research results and associated vocabulary provide precise, purposeful, quality wise, competitive advantage and farsightedness vision in the field of strategic human resource behavior in any organization.

We hope the research will provide many answers to those who have concerns in the area of such type of studies.

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APPENDIX 1: CORRELATION MATRIX

Correlation Matrix ^a																	
Correlation	VAR00001	VAR00002	VAR00003	VAR00004	VAR00005	VAR00006	VAR00007	VAR00008	VAR00009	VAR00010	VAR00011	VAR00012	VAR00013	VAR00014	VAR00015	VAR00016	VAR00017
	1.000	.279	.141	.200	.211	.250	.121	.262	.246	.200	.281	.125	.178	.230	.215	.234	.236
		1.000	.148	.286	.417	.242	.335	.349	.189	.154	.277	.309	.493	.412	-.015	.174	.374
			1.000	.425	.342	.407	.321	.374	.245	.011	.270	.062	.255	.063	.494	.080	-.103
				1.000	.348	.266	.443	.234	.119	.111	.355	.219	.420	.305	.339	.067	.089
					1.000	.348	.444	.331	.221	.236	.321	.337	.325	.320	.304	.007	.026
						1.000	.550	.107	.060	-.104	.108	-.021	.141	.217	.127	.012	.193
							1.000	.303	.181	.013	.094	.192	.378	.435	.153	.098	.036
								1.000	.433	.111	.370	.175	.236	.452	.379	.039	-.238
									1.000	.337	.119	.053	.177	.177	.424	.190	.098
										1.000	.174	.213	.109	.188	.130	-.138	-.018
											1.000	.566	.239	.211	.279	.073	-.015
												1.000	.198	.261	.135	.221	.067
													1.000	.329	.068	.092	.165
														1.000	-.014	.028	.177
															1.000	.214	-.142
																1.000	.439
																	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)		.015	.140	.061	.051	.026	.177	.021	.028	.062	.014	.168	.085	.037	.048	.035	.034
		.015		.127	.013	.000	.030	.004	.003	.072	.117	.015	.008	.000	.455	.089	.001
			.140	.127		.000	.004	.001	.006	.001	.028	.465	.018	.317	.023	.314	.000
			.061	.013	.000		.003	.019	.000	.035	.181	.198	.003	.045	.000	.008	.004
			.051	.000	.004	.003		.003	.000	.005	.044	.034	.006	.004	.005	.006	.009
			.026	.030	.001	.019	.003		.000	.205	.322	.212	.203	.435	.140	.047	.164
			.177	.004	.006	.000	.000		.000	.209	.082	.461	.235	.069	.001	.000	.119
			.021	.003	.001	.035	.005	.205	.009		.000	.196	.002	.088	.034	.000	.001
			.028	.072	.028	.181	.044	.322	.082	.000		.004	.180	.341	.086	.086	.000
			.062	.117	.465	.198	.034	.212	.461	.196	.004		.090	.050	.201	.074	.159
			.014	.015	.018	.003	.006	.203	.235	.002	.180	.090		.000	.032	.052	.015
			.168	.008	.317	.045	.004	.435	.069	.088	.341	.050	.000		.063	.021	.150
			.085	.000	.023	.000	.005	.140	.001	.034	.086	.201	.032	.063		.005	.300
			.037	.000	.314	.008	.006	.047	.000	.000	.086	.074	.052	.021	.005		.457
			.048	.455	.000	.004	.009	.164	.119	.001	.000	.159	.015	.150	.300	.457	
			.035	.089	.270	.305	.477	.465	.227	.383	.071	.144	.287	.044	.241	.417	.049
			.034	.001	.214	.247	.423	.068	.392	.033	.227	.445	.455	.304	.101	.087	.137

a. Determinant = .002